

Supplementary material - Interspeech 2025

Paper ID: 1245

Title: Oral Reading Errors by Grade 3 Children in Indian Schools: A Hindi-English Perspective

Abstract: We present an analysis of reading errors on a manually transcribed dataset of Grade 3 students (N=595) who read aloud level-appropriate passages in English and Hindi. Substitutions are categorised as word or non-word errors. Further, substitutions are analysed using grapheme/phoneme sequence matching and assigned typical reading error types such as initial part matches, final part matches and scaffolding errors. We compare the distribution of error categories for the two languages and discuss underlying language-dependent decoding strategies. We also apply the analysis methodology to identify the percentage scaffolding errors per utterance given its usefulness for reading assessment. Finally, we extend our work to its practical application for diagnostics by testing an automatic phone recognition system on our task.

Text Prompts

English

The Lost Sheep (125 words)

Once, there lived a shepherd in a village. He was a kind and good man. He had a hundred sheep. One day, he took the sheep to the riverside. There was a lot of grass there for the sheep. In the evening, the shepherd took them back home. He counted the sheep. There were only ninety-nine! One sheep was lost. The shepherd was sad.

He went out looking for the lost sheep. He walked all the way back to the river. At last, late in the night, he found the sheep in a bush. The bush was full of thorns. He got the sheep out and carried it home. He was happy. He showed the sheep to his friends. All of them were happy too.

Hindi

भूखी चिड़िया (132 words)

सालों पहले एक घंटाघर में टीकू चिड़िया अपने माता-पिता और पाँच भाइयों के साथ रहती थी। टीकू चिड़िया छोटी सी थी। उसके पंख मुलायम थे। उसकी माँ ने उसे घंटाघर की ताल पर चहकना सिखाया था। घंटाघर के पास ही एक घर था, जिसमें पक्षियों से प्यार करने वाली एक महिला रहती थी। वह टीकू चिड़िया और उसके परिवार के लिए रोज रोटी का टुकड़ा डालती थी।

एक दिन वह बीमार पड़ गई और उसकी मौत हो गई। टीकू चिड़िया और उसका पूरा परिवार उस औरत के खाने पर निर्भर था। अब उनके पास खाने के लिए कुछ नहीं था और न ही वो अपने लिए खाना जुटाने के लिए कुछ करते हैं। एक दिन भूख से बेहाल होने पर टीकू चिड़िया के पिता ने कीड़ों का शिकार करने का फैसला किया।

Error categories in orthographic and phonological mode for English and Hindi

Language	Word	Substitution (transliteration for english only)	Error type (orthographic)	Word phoneme sequence	Substitution phoneme sequence	Error type (phonological)
English	went	विन्ट (vint)	final correct	W EH N T	W IH N T	scaffolding
English	carried	कियर्ड (kiyard)	final correct	K AE R IY D	K IH Y AH R D	scaffolding
English	sheep	सिप (sip)	scaffolding	SH IY P	S IH P	final correct
English	evening	everything	scaffolding	IY W N IH NG	EH W R IY TH IH NG	final correct
English	thorns	ट्रौन्स (trows)	scaffolding	TH AO R N S	T R AO N S	final correct
English	sheep	shape	initial correct	SH IY P	SH EY P	scaffolding
English	evening	निविनिग (nivinig)	final correct	IY W N IH NG	N IH W IH N IH G	some overlap
English	there	upon	other	DH EY R	AH P AO N	other
Hindi	शिकार	सिकार	final correct	sh ii k AA r	s ii k AA r	final correct
Hindi	किया	लिया	final correct	k ii y AA	l ii y AA	final correct
Hindi	घंटाघर	घंटाद	initial correct	gh aa q T AA gh aa r	gh aa q T AA d	initial correct
Hindi	टींकू	टींगु	initial correct	T II q k UU	T II q g uu	initial correct
Hindi	साथ	जात	some overlap	s AA th	j AA t	some overlap
Hindi	रहती	देखते	some overlap	r aa hh aa t II	d ee kh aa t ee	some overlap
Hindi	घंटाघर	चंडाघर	final correct	gh aa q T AA gh aa r	ch aa q D AA gh aa r	final correct
Hindi	पर	पार	(not computed, length of word <3)	p aa r	p AA r	scaffolding
Hindi	सिखाया	सिकाया	scaffolding	s ii kh AA y AA	s ii k AA y AA	scaffolding

Error categories by manual and automatic method for English and Hindi

Confusion matrix Manual vs Automatic Method (English)

Confusion matrix Manual vs Automatic Method (Hindi)

Language	Word	Word phone sequence	Substitution	Manual phoneme sequence	Error type (manual)	Automatic phoneme sequence	Error type (automatic)
English	ninety	nightly	N AY N T IY	N AY T L IY	scaffolding_error	N AY T L IY	scaffolding_error
English	nine	nice	N AY N	N AY S	initial_correct	N AY S	initial_correct
English	lost	lots	L AO S T	L AO T S	initial_correct	L AO T S	initial_correct
English	shepherd	शिपेड	SH EY P AH R D	SH IH P EY D	scaffolding_error	SH IY P EY D	scaffolding_error
English	lost	lot	L AO S T	L AO T	scaffolding_error	L AO T S	initial_correct
English	walked	walk	W AO K D	W AO K	initial_correct	W AO K	initial_correct
English	last	lots	L AA S T	L AO T S	initial_correct	L AO T S	initial_correct
English	bush	बश	B UH SH	B AH SH	scaffolding_error	B AH S	initial_correct
English	thorns	थ्रॉन्स	TH AO R N S	TH R AO N S	scaffolding_error	S AO N S	Final_correct
English	carried	cred	K AE R IY D	K R EH D	scaffolding_error	K R EY D	scaffolding_error
English	friends	friend	F R EH N D S	F R EH N D	initial_correct	F R EH N D	initial_correct
English	were	where	W EH R	W HH EY R	scaffolding_error	W EH R	scaffolding_error
Hindi	टीकू	टीकू	T II q k UU	T II k UU	scaffolding_error	T II k uu	initial_correct
Hindi	कीड़ों	किरो	k II D oo q	k ii r oo	initial_correct	II r oo	some_overlap
Hindi	टीकू	टीकू	T II q k UU	T II k UU	scaffolding_error	T ii k uu	initial_correct
Hindi	निभर	निभर	n ii r bh aa r	n ii bh aa r	scaffolding_error	n ii bh aa r	scaffolding_error
Hindi	टीकू	टीकू	T II q k UU	T II k UU	scaffolding_error	T ii s k oo	initial_correct
Hindi	उसकी	उसके	uu s aa k II	uu s aa k ee	initial_correct	uu s aa k ee	initial_correct
Hindi	उनके	उसने	uu n aa k ee	uu s aa n ee	scaffolding_error	uu s aa n ee	scaffolding_error
Hindi	खाना	खाने	kh AA n AA	kh AA n ee	initial_correct	kh AA n ee k aa	initial_correct
Hindi	जुटाने	जुगाड	j uu T AA n ee	j uu g AA D	initial_correct	j uu g AA D	initial_correct
Hindi	करते	करती	k aa r aa t ee	k aa r aa t II	initial_correct	k aa r t II	initial_correct
Hindi	बेहाल	हाल	b ee hh AA I	hh AA I	Final_correct	hh AA I	Final_correct
Hindi	शिकार	सिकार	sh ii k AA r	s ii k AA r	Final_correct	sh w II k AA r	scaffolding_error
Hindi	टीकू	डिकु	T II q k UU	D ii k uu	some_overlap	D ee k UU	Final_correct

Word nonword errors in English and Hindi

Language	Word	Substitution	Error type
English	looking	look	word
English	last	laas	nonword
English	bush	bash	nonword
English	thorns	towns	word
English	carried	cried	word
English	showed	should	word
English	friends	friend	word
English	walked	vowlked	nonword
English	all	and	word
Hindi	उसका	उसने	word
Hindi	पूरा	पूरी	word
Hindi	न	ना	word
Hindi	वो	व	word
Hindi	जुटाने	जुटने	word
Hindi	शिकार	सिकार	nonword
Hindi	करने	करना	word
Hindi	वह	वो	nonword
Hindi	निर्भर	निभर	nonword
Hindi	न	ना	word